

THE REACTIVITY OF THIOL GROUPS IN PROTEINS. PART III. HUMAN, BOVINE AND HORSE SERUM-ALBUMINS

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Specific thiol reagents of different strengths and types were allowed to react on human, bovine and horse serum-albumins, both native and denatured, in 7.5 *M* urea solution. An attempt has been made to interpret the discrepancies observed in the action of the different reagents.

Human, bovine and horse serum-albumins have much in common. A M.W. of 66,000 has somewhat arbitrarily been adopted in our calculations for the three proteins, but for each it corresponds with reliable recent determinations (Edsall, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1954, 12, 253).

From physico-chemical investigations, the shape of the three native albumins seems best represented by a prolate ellipsoid with an axial ratio of about 4/1. Determinations for bovine (Onclay *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1947, 51, 184) and horse albumins (Neurath and Saum, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1939, 123, 347) point to 145-150 Å for the major axis and 34-38 Å for the minor. One terminal N-group-aspartic acid- has been detected in the three albumins alike, without necessarily implying the presence of a single polypeptide. A complete amino-acid analysis has been made for human and bovine albumins. They indicate a close overall similarity of composition, with a few significant differences. The sequences are surely not identical (Thomson, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1954, 208, 565). Analyses of sulphur amino-acids of the three albumins have been made. The % cystine is practically identical (32-34 groups). Cysteine and methionine contents vary: in human albumin there are 4 cysteine and 6 methionine groups/Mol. (Brand *et al.*, *Ann. Rev. Biochem.*, 1947, 16, 223), in bovine albumin 2.5 (Goebel *et al.*, *J. Exptl. Med.*, 1949, 89, 479) and 4 (Lewis *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1950, 183, 23) respectively, and in horse albumin 3 cysteine but no methionine at all (Brand *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1941, 141, 999). The structure of bovine albumin alone has been studied by X-rays (Riley and Arndt, *Nature*, 1952, 169, 138). Pauling's α -helixes or a very closely similar pattern would represent correctly the main polypeptidic configuration. From the close similarities of properties, shape and composition of the 3 albumins, it can safely be inferred that all the three are best represented by α -helixes. They contain about 550 amino-acids, including 27-29 proline residues. With 1.5 Å per radical, the molecules are likely to consist of a bundle of the six segments of a helix bent back on itself, closely packed together and eventually intertwined.

EXPERIMENTAL

The methods of determination of the SH groups by silver, *p*-chloromercuribenzoate (*p*-ClHg), ferricyanide, iodoacetic acid and iodoacetamide have been previously described (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 285, 289).

A human serum-albumin preparation of Poviet, Amsterdam, was used. Concentrations were determined on the basis of a % N₂ of 15.95 (Brand *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, 1947) by

semimicro Kjeldahl. Bovine serum-albumin was prepared by fractional precipitation with alcohol at a low temperature, according to Cohn (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 459). It was homogeneous in the electrophoresis at p_H 8.7 and ionic strength 0.1, but gave one and even two minor components at a lower p_H . A %N of 16.1 was adopted (Lewis *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Horse serum-albumin was prepared by fractional precipitation with $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ and recrystallised thrice according to Hermans (Thesis, Louven Univ., 1951). It showed two components in equal proportions in the electrophoresis at p_H 7.26 and ionic strength 0.1. A %N of 15.9 was adopted (Neurath *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1941, **138**, 411). Denaturations were performed as described previously (this *Journal*, 1956, **33**, 285). In order to avoid discrepancies arising from differences in the conditions of preparation, for each protein, all the determinations were performed on aliquots of an identical preparation.

TABLE I

[No. denotes number of determinations]

	Ag $(NH_3)_2^+$		p -ClHgb.		Fe $(CN)_6^{3-}$		ICH ₂ COO ⁻	ICH ₂ CONH ₂
	SH/M.	No.	SH/M.	No.	SH/M (?)	No.	SH/M.	SH/M.
Human serum-albumin : Native.								
0.4		6	0.05	4	1	3	0	0.3
0.4	Lit. (Benesch, <i>Arch. Biochem.</i> , 1948, 19 , 35).							
0.7	(Jensen, <i>J. Biol. Chem.</i> , 1950, 188 , 411; Weissman, <i>ibid.</i> , 1950, 187 , 153).							
Denatured in urea 7.5 M.								
0.2		5	0.2	4	1.1	3	0 (?)	0
	x: id after 70 hours of contact urea-protein							
Bovine serum-albumin : Native.								
0.2		11	0.45	6	1.2	2	0.2	0.2
0	(Rosenberg, <i>Anal. Chem.</i> , 1950, 22 , 1186).							
0.7	(Jensen, <i>loc. cit.</i> Benesch, <i>loc. cit.</i>).							
Denatured in urea 7.5 M								
0.2		3	0.35	8	1.1	1	1.8 (?)	0.6
0	(Rosenberg, <i>loc. cit.</i>).							
Horse serum-albumin : Native.								
0.6		10	0	6	1.2	6	0.5	0.5
Denatured in urea 7.5 M.								
0.1		3	0	6	0.8x	4	0.5	0.5
	x: id after 24 hours of contact urea-protein.							

Iodoacetamide-iodoacetate

It is impossible to determine by extrapolation a reliable value for the free SH groups, reacting with iodoacetate in the denatured human albumin. It may be surmised however, that this number will be at most equal to the number of SH groups reacting

with iodoacetamide in the same protein. The latter has a more rapid reaction with the SH groups than iodoacetate. The SH reaction is completely masked here by other reactions, particularly with the amino groups. The slope of the curve expressing the

FIG. 1

Equivalents of I^- liberated in terms of time, in the reactions of native and urea-denatured human serum albumin with iodoacetate (●) and iodoacetamide (○), $p_H = 6.96$. Temp. = 25° .

FIG. 2

Eqv. of I^- liberated in terms of time for native and urea-denatured bovine albumin with iodoacetate (●) and iodoacetamide (○). $p_H = 6.96$. Temp. = 23° . The curves for horse albumin start at $0.5 I^-$ liberated at time = 0, but soon practically coincide with the corresponding curves for the bovine albumin.

liberated iodine in terms of time of reaction between denatured albumin and iodoacetate remains very steep to time = 2 hours ($23 I^-$), to become later less and less pronounced (after 24 hours: $33 I^-$). The reaction of NH_2 groups is much more rapid with iodoacetate than with iodoacetamide, while methionine reactions proceed at sensibly equal speed. We can thus infer from the comparison of the different curves that in a $7.5 M$ urea solution, a large number of NH_2 groups from lysine, amides etc. are unmasked.

The interpretation of these curves calls for remarks identical with those made for human albumin, though the increase of the amino-reaction with iodoacetate brought about by denaturation is here less important. Comparisons of the binding power for methyl orange etc. at different p_H for human and bovine serum-albumins had lead Klotz *et al.* (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, 56, 77) to similar conclusions.

The values recorded for the $p\text{-ClHg}$ reactions are subject to caution. Serum-albumin solutions are slightly yellow and an exact determination of the end-point by the appearance of the rosy colour of the reaction of an excess cysteine with nitroprusside is difficult. Some data from the literature cast a doubt on our data for the human albumin reaction: human albumin first put in contact with $p\text{-ClHg}$ gives no reaction with silver (Benesch, *loc. cit.* Weissmann, *loc. cit.*) and two molecules of the mercaptalbumin fraction of human albumin are bound by the bulky bifunctional Hg reagent of Straessle (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 504) to form a dimer. Both human (Hughes, *loc. cit.*) and bovine (Lontie *et al.*, *Arch. Int. Physiol.*, 1951, 62, 556) albumins form a dimer with Hg.

From its reaction with amandin, we showed that ferricyanide was probably no specific reagent of the SH groups in all proteins (this *Journal*, 1956, **33**, 285) as it was in ovalbumin (Anson, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1939, **22**, 247). The determinations on the three serum-albumins seem to confirm this finding. It is unlikely that SH groups which fail to react with other oxidising agents, silver and p -ClHgB would react with ferricyanide. Besides, denaturation in 7.5 *M* urea does not affect the reaction. After 70 hours of contact between protein and urea, the number of SH groups determined would normally decrease due to the oxidation by air of part of them; yet, the ferricyanide reaction of denatured human albumin is unaffected. The data seem to indicate the presence of one oxidisable group per molecule, different from the SH, in the three serum albumins, native as well as denatured.

Unlike ovalbumin, denaturation in a 7.5 *M* urea solution does not bring about in the three serum-albumins an increase of the number of reactive SH groups. The change of structure must be less thorough. After denaturation by relatively mild procedures, the α -helix structure remains essentially intact (Riley *et al.*, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1953, **B141**, 93). Physico-chemical data show that denaturation does not bring about a total uncoiling, but rather an expanding of the serum-albumin molecule (Birefringence: Foster *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 6044. Viscosity and diffusion: Neurath and Saum, *loc. cit.*). The protein keeping the shape of an ellipsoid, the major axis would be doubled while the minor axis would become about $20\text{\AA}$ (Neurath and Saum, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1939, **128**, 347; 1941, **138**, 411; 1942, **142**, 249). Things happen as if, in the bundle of 6 helixes, 2 subunits of three closely interconnected helixes (Pauling's three stranded ropes?) were more loosely bound together by electrostatic forces and hydrogen bonds. Hence, the great sensitivity to p_H and ionic strength or such low concentrations of urea as 2*M*. The protein would open or split lengthwise by the repulsion of the two subunits, which at the limit would separate by rotation around the peptide linking the two subunits (Harrington *et al.*, *Biochem. J.*, 1956, **62**, 569). This hypothesis would explain that SH groups masked in the native albumin could remain so after denaturation, and that other groups, present in large numbers, eventually engaged in some interhelix bonds in the native albumin, would become easily accessible to their reagents, as denaturation proceeds. Such are the numerous amino groups reacting easily with iodoacetate and binding a larger number of organic anions after denaturation (Klotz, *Cold Spring Harbour Symp. Quant. Biol.*, 1950, **14**, 97). Literature shows an instance of a similar increase in the availability of disulphide groups (Neurath and Saum, *loc. cit.*, 1939). Tyrosine (Klotz, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, No. 13, 189) and amino-groups (Hermans, *loc. cit.*) become available in increasing numbers with increasing p_H on the alkaline side.

A decrease is observed in the silver reactions of human (0.25 instead of 0.45 SH/M) and horse (0.1 instead of 0.6 SH/M) albumins after denaturation. Bovine (0.2 instead of 0.5 SH/M) and horse (0.1 instead of 0.5 SH/M) denatured albumins have a smaller number of SH groups reacting with silver than with iodoacetamide. This could be explained by a spontaneous oxidation by air at the higher p_H (9.25/7): of the silver reaction as in the case of ovalbumin (this *Journal*, 1956, **33**, 289). Such oxidations, however, seem to

imply here the formation of intermolecular disulphide bonds. This possibility should not be ruled out and is advocated by Huggins *et al.* (*Nature*, 1951, 187, 592) to explain gel formation in 5.5 M urea solutions of bovine albumin, while Robert *et al.* (*Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, No. 13, 49) observed an oxidation by air of the SH groups of horse albumin at high p_{H} . Ammonium ions could also affect unfavourably the SH titration (Greenstein and Edsall, *ibid.*, 1940, 133, 397). The new method of Benesch *et al.* (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1955, 216, 663), using the tris-(hydroxymethyl)-amino-methane-silver complex instead of the NH_3 one, allows to work at neutrality and to observe an increase in reacting SH groups upon denaturation by urea (from 0.67 to 1.04 SH/M).

Differences of reactivity of the SH groups of identical serum-albumins with different reagents can be explained by the same reasons advocated in the case of ovalbumin (Lontie *et al.*, *loc cit.*).

From the reactions of Hg on serum-albumins, only one component of the heterogeneous albumins in the native state seems to possess a reactive SH group: the "mercaptalbumin" (Hughes *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, *et seq.*). This explains why the number of available SH groups in serum-albumins is not expressed by even an approximate small integer. The proportion in which mercaptalbumin is present in each sample could explain differences observed between literature data for silver titrations of the same albumin, prepared according to different methods. Fully significant comparisons call for a fractionation of the components of the serum-albumins prior to the determination of their SH groups.

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